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Ashwini Ranjan & Ashwani Kumar Upadhyay

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Value co-creation by interactive AI in fashion E-commerce

Ashwini Ranjan and Ashwani Kumar Upadhyay

Symbiosis Institute of Media and Communication, Symbiosis International (Deemed University), Pune, India

ABSTRACT

This study focuses on the role of AI chatbots in facilitating co-creation between brands and consumers and explores user's attitudes and perceptions toward AI stylists/chatbots. This study discusses the process of artificial intelligence stylist/chatbot consideration from the beginning of purchase intention to adding the product to the wishlist for the future or buying it directly to understand its value. The authors used purposive sampling and in-depth interviews to gather qualitative data from 25 respondents. The findings indicate a need for tailored suggestions and concern about several optional recommendations, particularly when integrating in-app with external platforms like Nykaafashion with WhatsApp. With its ability to provide personalized recommendations and effective interactions, AI-driven chatbots significantly improve e-commerce personalization. However, they frequently fall short when answering complicated questions and cannot offer the same level of empathy and emotional connection that human representatives can. The study emphasizes the potential of chatbots to improve online customer experiences, increase conversion rates, and foster brand loyalty. This study also offers recommendations for future research and strategies for e-commerce businesses to strengthen their competitive edge in the market. Future recommendations include incorporating emotional AI and multimodal interfaces in the chatbot.

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Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) has transformed how many businesses operate and has become a buzzword with big data and machine learning breakthroughs. AI excels in pattern recognition, social network involvement prediction, and artistic creation are among the tasks where AI excels (Lee & Li, 2023). Many businesses have implemented incredibly potent AI-powered chatbots to communicate with clientele. Conversational agents are unique for communication between a firm and its customers because they provide affordances by which services that are always accessible can be delivered and information can be searched and visualized. Examples of such developments in machine-human interactions are Apple's Siri and Amazon's Alexa, and their proliferation is predicted (Murtarelli et al., 2021).

Organizations use conversations to build trust that underpins cooperation and collaboration, even when trust is founded only on transactional understanding, such as exchanging a product for a monetary token. Conversations are unique in chatbot-based environments because they are tools for data integration and information gathering (Murtarelli et al., 2021). Owing to their human-like characteristics, chatbots encourage digital users to trust them with the transactions they carry out and additional personal and other information.

Active user participation in conversations and transactions is encouraged through interactivity (Xu et al., 2022). When a chatbot can offer customers two-way contact and fast access to product information, they are likely to take advantage of it to complete their tasks. Customers can take advantage of a company's services concurrently because they usually approach chatbots to help with problems or more product information.

CONTACT Ashwani Kumar Upadhyay Symbiosis Institute of Media and Communication, Symbiosis International (Deemed University), Gram: Lavale, Pune 411045, India

Both authors have contributed to this research article equally.

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A chatbot is a valuable tool that businesses can use to offer clients easily accessible services. Consumers use chatbots to research products and find solutions to problems; hence, anywhere, anytime connectivity, information association, visibility, and interaction help users accomplish their goals. Managers should instead concentrate on how customers assess the features that chatbots provide rather than the features themselves, which has gradually been developed to support an enormous array of interactions between customers and brand identification with the chatbot versus identification with the brand, to investigate customer loyalty toward a chatbot as a service. In this application space, chatbots provide real-time, one-on-one sales of goods and services tailored to each customer's demand (Sidlauskiene et al., 2023). The purpose of using chatbots going forward in the context of luxury brands is to align the chatbot e-service idea with luxury brand values, which provide customers with better service and strengthen the quality of their relationship with customers (Jin & Youn, 2023).

These two essential aspects of stereotypes facilitate the preservation of customer-firm ties and the improvement of customer involvement. Competent chatbots can assist users in quickly and effectively resolving issues, and are a valuable tool for providing value through interactions. This is where providing quick fixes and brief, straightforward discussions helps improve chatbot skills. Managers should, therefore, take advantage of chatbot affordances to attract customers by fostering interactions between chatbots and customers that increase brand loyalty (Lee & Li, 2023). It is important to understand the introduction of such chatbots and their workflow in the fashion industry for the brand's purpose to have a successful customer acquisition, loyalty etc.

By investigating how AI-driven chatbots might support co-creation between businesses and customers in e-commerce environments, this study seeks to close these gaps. This perspective will be used to analyze how users view and interact with AI-powered products, as well as how chatbot design affects how well co-creation shapes customer experiences. There is a need to understand consumer confidence in emerging AI-driven chatbots and offer a theoretical framework to maximize customer-business interactions by strategically leveraging E-commerce technology. Though AI-powered chatbots are becoming more and more common in e-commerce, little is known about how these technologies help or improve co-creation between customers and brands. Although conventional co-creation methods have been studied, nothing is known about the precise function AI chatbots that play in this dynamic industry. Furthermore, nothing is known about how customers view and feel about co-creation with AI chatbots in comparison to human encounters. The recent addition of chatbots in E-commerce apps helps to investigate how users interact with AI chatbots at different points in their interaction journey, from when they first see the chatbot feature to when they complete transactions or decide which goods to add to their Wishlist. It explores various aspects of this relationship, such as how simple or complex users find chatbots to use, the difficulties they face along the way, the degree to which chatbots affect users' research and decision-making processes, their patterns of purchase behaviour, and the overall engagement experience while considering future viewpoints. The study also examined how different strategies used by other brands for their virtual personal stylists could affect customer trust and engagement.

Literature review

Joseph Weizenbaum, a scientist at MIT, developed Eliza, the first chatbot in the 1960s. By answering user phrases in an interrogative manner, Eliza mimicked the functions of a psychotherapist. Despite having limited communication capabilities, it has impacted the eventual development of chatbots. Eliza imitated a conversation using a pattern matching and substitution methodology (Sidlauskiene et al., 2023). The fashion industry has been compelled to accelerate its digital transformation and put conventional offline services online, partly because of the COVID-19 epidemic (Landim et al., 2022). Sabanoglu (2024) reported that 77% of UK retail companies use chatbots to deploy AI in e-commerce. Businesses that sell to consumers (B2C) incorporate chatbots as virtual shopping assistants more frequently to provide their customers with faster, tailored online shopping experiences (Landim et al., 2022).

Multimodal chatbots can be used to combine textual chatbot interfaces with visual media. By establishing multimodal domain knowledge and enhancing a fashion chatbot that can comprehend the semantics of a product image, adjust the attributes during back-end retrieval, provide matched

suggestions, and produce responses in many modalities (Marulli et al., 2018). To deliver more tailored suggestions, take advantage of multimodality to consider extra-rational consumer characteristics, such as attitudes, emotions, likes, and dislikes. Virtual assistants can also be trained to impersonate salespeople and stylists (Morotti et al., 2020).

Models such as the use and gratification theory (U&G) and the Technological Adoption Model (TAM) have been used to evaluate chatbot adoption, with a primary focus on perceived utility, ease of use, and enjoyment (Kasilingam, 2020; Rese et al., 2020). According to Morsi (2023), media consumption can fulfil people's social and psychological requirements, broken down into five categories: stress-free, cognitive, emotive, integrative, and social. Technical satisfaction has become increasingly important in recent years as it is required for e-commerce activities (Morsi, 2023). This depends on whether people can use the technology to achieve their desired results precisely and successfully. In the case of chatbots, this is highly reliant on chatbot-to-human interaction or 'authenticity' being satisfied (Morsi, 2023). An entity's ability to feel human emotions and how those feelings may influence its decision-making is known as emotionality. One of the critical components of the theory of mind perception framework and the ability of entities to feel real emotions is connected to this idea of emotionality (Dhavraj & Ndoro, 2023). The adoption of chatbots relies on social presence, a characteristic of human interaction, and functional and pleasant characteristics. Privacy concerns may also affect the acceptance of chatbots (Murtarelli et al., 2021), and this influence may vary among different populations.

Additionally, according to Lee and Li (2023), AI-driven chatbots offer visibility, interaction, information association, and anytime-anywhere connectivity. This study examined how chatbots might show information in text, images, videos, or hyperlinks to all users. This information is presented visually, which promotes the best possible usage of chatbots. Similarly, consumers can freely utilize appropriate services via chatbots quickly and effortlessly. Users' active engagement in conversations and transactions is encouraged through interactivity. When a chatbot allows customers to interact in both directions and has fast access to product information, they are more likely to use it to carry out activities. Customers are encouraged by an information association to actively utilize chatbot services, allowing them to solve their problems (Lee & Li, 2023). AI-based chatbots have verbal anthropomorphic cues that encourage users to view products offered and purchased through chatbots as more personalized, which adds to conversational commerce contexts (Sidlauskiene et al., 2023). Anthropomorphism and privacy are two review-derived factors that affect the credibility of chatbots. Anthropomorphism caters to the tendency of humans to attribute human characteristics to AI chatbots (Dhavraj & Ndoro, 2023) as the quality of conversation is impacted. The acquired data regarding consumers' intention to continue using a company's chatbot are timely and relevant, as continuance intention is increasingly crucial in an ever-growing competitive IT landscape and smart retailing (Jin & Youn, 2023). The level of perceived accessibility and ease of use of chatbots is known to be convenient. In consumer behavior, situational loneliness is a factor that influences consumers' perceptions of products as more personalized and valuable (Sidlauskiene et al., 2023). In addition, chatbots have hedonic factors, and consumers spend their free time online. Hence, enjoyment perception significantly influences user behavior when buying digital products (Morsi, 2023). Technology is still in its early phases of development and might need to be more trustworthy and functional, which is called immature technology. Technology's perceived immaturity is an element that can affect its reception. Users may be less likely to accept a technology if they believe it is still in its infancy, because they may doubt its stability, functionality, and dependability. According to Morsi (2023), chatbot technology is still in its infancy, and there is ongoing doubt regarding its potential applications, as evidenced by its poor text recognition accuracy, inability to comprehend voice input, and lack of ability to provide accurate responses.

The requirements outlined by Bowen and Morosan (2018) state that an automated chatbot is necessary to generate value for consumers. It must first be created using an eye-catching user interface that evokes feelings and thoughts. Digital devices, such as computers, tablets, smartphones, and other comparable gadgets, can facilitate these chatbot interfaces. Second, it must be sufficiently customizable to suit various user groups. Third, its operation must resemble that of other modern platforms. In their varied forms, these consumer contributions serve as experiential elements of the value-creation process and may ensure innovation. Vargo and Lusch (2004) further state that experiential components are

essential for actual value to be realized throughout creation and consumption. Businesses aim to have deliberate conversations with customers to gather insights and improve their services (Solakis et al., 2022). These are the few critical factors that relate to the usage of virtual stylists and brand image by creating value for each other.

Theoretical lens

According to Prahalad and Ramaswamy (2004a), the first step in the Value Co-Creation process is for organizations to shift from a firm-centric to a customer-centric perspective, requiring firms to reorganize their fundamental operations to engage customers in a deliberate dialogue. Participation in the co-creation process and knowledge sharing are encouraged through dialogue. According to Prahalad and Ramaswamy (2004b), dialogue involves both the firm and the consumer's tendency to act, and their engagement and interaction. Through communication, both sides can work together to resolve divergent concerns and create win-win solutions. Together, the three parameters of dialogue, convenience, and transparency allow customers to measure the harm and advantages of being active co-creators.

Customers provide useful information to re-strategize their operations and revamp their offers as they share their consumption experiences (Kristensson et al., 2008). In this way, the company can create metrics to evaluate suitable value propositions and build its processes to match those of customers (Payne et al., 2007). The idea of co-creation, in which customers actively influence the quality of their brand interactions and the purchasing experiences they have, is fundamental to this evolution. Co-creation has traditionally been studied in relation to human-to-human interactions, but the addition of AI to this process creates new research opportunities.

This study applies value co-creation theory as a theoretical framework to understand how AI enhances the value of Fashion E-commerce platforms. Value co-creation theory (Galvagno & Dalli, 2014) emphasizes how businesses and customers work together to create value. AI may support value co-creation in the context of fashion apparel and apps by enabling firms to use customer data and preferences to deliver personalized experiences, optimize supply chains, and offer specialized services. This idea strongly emphasizes the value of engaged and active customers during the value-generation process. These ideas offer frameworks and viewpoints to understand the dynamics of AI-driven value co-creation in the e-commerce industry. The co-creation becomes easy as the motivation and challenges of using chatbot/VPS in a changed buying pattern by engaging to understand the value being provided/gained from both ends like brands VPS and consumer. These ideas can help digital retail firms understand consumer behaviour, motives, and preferences and create marketing campaigns that adhere to customization, experience, and stable consumer relationships.

Methodology

This exploratory study used a qualitative research approach and followed Creswell's (1998) recommendations. In line with Thyer's (2010) suggestions, semi-structured interviews with online consumers (Early Adopters or Early Majority) were utilized in this study to gather qualitative data. In a semi-structured interview, the interviewer posed many open-ended pre-planned questions. By using suitable probes and a systematic approach to ask predetermined questions, the interviewer can obtain insightful information about the subject of their inquiry or investigation. Informed consent was obtained verbally during the interview from study participants for the online interviews. A pilot study involving three participants was conducted to assess the aptness and relevance of the questionnaires. A discussion guide (Annexure 1) with open-ended questions was developed and finalized based on the pilot study results aided in eliciting suitable responses from participants who were digitally savvy consumers. Based on the results of the pilot study, an open-ended discussion guide (Annexure 1) was developed and finalized. Relevant answers were obtained from participants who engaged in online shopping using open-ended and essential questions. The interviews were taped utilizing recording technology with prior authorization and relevant notes. Online interviews were coded and transcription was performed after an average of twenty-five minutes, proceeded by thematic data analysis. This study ethics was approved by the Research

Table 1. Details of the participant's.

Participants	Gender	Profession	Age
P1	Female	Content Writer and Freelancer	28
P2	Male	Senior software engineer	27
P3	Female	Data analyst	26
P4	Male	Graphic designer and owner of the design studio	27
P5	Male	Advertising Manager	28
P6	Male	Lawyer	28
P7	Female	Completed Post Graduation	27
P8	Female	Research Associate	26
P9	Female	Fashion Influencer	27
P10	Male	Civil Service Aspirant	29
P11	Female	Lawyer	28
P12	Female	Research Assistant	29
P13	Female	Security Specialist	28
P14	Female	Senior Data Analyst	32
P15	Female	Senior Software Engineer	32
P16	Female	Junior Software Developer	26
P17	Male	Sales Manager	28
P18	Male	MBA student	26
P19	Female	Subject Matter Expert	27
P20	Male	Executive MBA Student	32
P21	Female	Medical Writer and Science Journalist	34
P22	Male	Principal Engineer	34
P23	Female	MBA student	26
P24	Female	Investment Banker	28
P25	Male	MBA Student	27

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Respondents

The respondents were professionals working in various industries and organizations or as freelance professionals. Table 1 contains details of the respondents who were selected using convenience and purposive sampling techniques. All participants were young millennials or Gen X working or staying in metro cities with hands-on usage of digital technologies daily. Most participants were media enthusiasts, lawyers, content writers, software engineers, academics, entrepreneurs, human resources specialists, or freelancers from India. The respondents have given their informed consent to participate in this study. The concept of saturation and other published research determine the sample size in qualitative investigations. Marshall et al. (2013) indicated that a sample size of 20 to 30 is sufficient for qualitative studies that employ grounded theory.

In the need for new insights, the qualitative researcher stopped interviewing individuals after saturation was reached. After the 22nd interview, there were no unexpected results, indicating data saturation. Hence, the sample size for this study was set to 25.

Procedure

The Researchers interviewed a young digitally sound professional by asking 14 questions from the made-up discussion guide. These questions ranged from their habit of the general perception of online shopping to questions on the adoption of AI-powered virtual personal stylists or chatbots regarding apparel purchases to understand the usefulness of managing the impact of such technology on consumer behavior. A deductive method was employed to classify and identify themes. This was a verbal interview conducted on Zoom. Furthermore, recordings of the personal interviews were decoded, transcribed, and analyzed. According to Creswell and Creswell (2018) recommendations for data coding, the replies were categorized and grouped thematically to identify underlying trends. The transcripts were summarized using an Excel document. However, the inter-coder reliability of the analysis was preserved.

Research question

RQ1: By changing traditional consumer approach and bending conventional patterns, how do chatbots and virtual personal stylists provide/gain value to/from the fashion experience?

RQ2: What are the most significant transformations that chatbots and virtual personal stylists have brought about in terms of customer interactions?

RQ3: How do chatbots and virtual personal stylists lead the way for future innovations in e-commerce?

Findings and discussion

The following section discusses the role of chatbots and virtual personal stylists in the e-commerce segment, this AI feature is a new introduction to apps, such as Myntra and Nykaafashion. Such large brands have impacted consumers by incorporating chatbots and virtual personal stylists.

Reasons for using virtual personal stylists

Understanding the intentions behind using chatbot-based or virtual personal stylists when contemplating or purchasing apparel is essential. The chatbot is a recent addition to fulfilling the needs of consumers through better suggestions and value-for-money purchases in the fashion apparel section. Participant 4 stated

I wanted to explore new things on the app, which might save time. Hence, I gave it a try. A new feature like this becomes unnoticeable when the consumer uses it for certain purchases.

Thus, many consumers learned about this feature from friends' recommendations, as in Participant 4. In contrast, Participant 3 used the Myntra Chatbot by surfing through the app and hovering over the icon. At first glance, this was customer service for many participants; consumers having issues with their purchases may contact them here. Participant 21 accidentally discovered it and was looking for occasion-based purchases, which might have helped with urgency.

Chatbot and virtual personal stylist usage

Any new introduction becomes a success or failure; during the budding stage, there is much speculation. Myntra and Nykaafashion in India have the first-mover advantage in this segment, and excellent and bitter experiences also impact consumer brand relations.

Participant 2 used Nykaafashion's stylist, and their experience was exceptional because of the good suggestions in the price bracket. It's a new feature that uses AI to get insights into people's accounts and suggest trends accordingly.

Most participants stay away from their hometowns; there will only sometimes be anyone advising them who might live alone in a city. This becomes an expert buddy who provides free services.

Participant 3 said, *"They narrowed the search by displaying the best option that might suit the offer. They can be approached for just a piece of extra advice or a valuable suggestion, they provide it right. With Korean pants, what looks good? Do these sneakers go?"*

Participant 4 pointed out, *"Even if I haven't bought the clothes right now, in the Nykaafashion app, the possibility of referring back to the conversation stays," and talked about its usefulness, too. Doing a regular search was like digging through the whole app while missing out on some exclusive or best options. Hence, this feature is handy.*

Participant 15 mentioned that *"this feature fulfils the aspirational aspect of the consumers, as the idea of consulting a stylist in day-to-day life is not possible for ordinary people, but these apps are making that happen."*

Participant 3 said, *"She prefers online to understand what is the latest trend and right now, as living in tier three cities, what we see that we are getting that fashion, which was in Delhi from like past five years today, it is true that the knowledge about the latest trends arrives late in tier 2 and tier 3 cities.*

Table 2. Emerging Themes reasons for use and preference for virtual personal stylist.

Themes	Sub-themes
Reasons for using virtual personal stylists	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Convenience and Accessibility: Participant 18 said, "Online shopping is convenient compared to physical stores because of the variety of options available, the time-saving aspects, etc." • Equitable Access and Inclusivity: Participant 3 said: "Coming from tier 3 city to Bangalore for work, trends arrive late." • Work-Life Balance and Time Constraints: Participant 2 said, "Being a senior software engineer, I don't have much time." • Preference for Online Platforms: Participant 6 says, "have been purchasing my clothes online for the past six to seven years and it's very easy compared to physical shopping."
Chatbot and Virtual Personal Stylist Usage	<p>Motivation to Consult Chatbots or Virtual Personal Stylists:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Convenience and Access to Expertise • Personalised Recommendations • Aspirational Aspect • Mixed Experiences • Curiosity and Exploration • Technical Limitations • Lack of Human Touch <p>Differences from Conventional In-Store Assistance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-Pushy Sales Approach • Freedom and Convenience • Absence of Emotional Quotient • Potential for Improvement • Technical Challenges • Lack of Transparency <p>Encouragement/Demotivation to Make Purchases with Chatbots or Virtual Stylists:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ease of Decision-Making • Reduced Time and Effort • Value Proposition • Continued Engagement • Dissatisfaction with Experience • Preference for Traditional Shopping

The chatbot is supposed to be a good initiative because it is in a budding stage."

Many participants appreciated this feature and were looking forward to using an upgraded version. Participant 10 said, *"When I asked for styles, it just showed me a vast collection of styles like a Google search, not according to my preference."*

The chatbot displays various options, which was not possible while searching manually because brands sometimes need to be visible due to multiple filters and sorting options being applied.

Participant 13 has a mixed experience in Nykaafashion; *"due to WhatsApp integration, it just opened a separate WhatsApp window as a personal stylist, and they asked for personal details again. Hence, the app needed to be more engaging; I prefer Myntra over NykaaFashion because everything is integrated."*

Contrary to this, participant 7 says, *"This becomes an advantage; doing it manually is hectic, but when it comes to chatting and behavioural aspects our generation is equipped with, it becomes convenient to use WhatsApp to communicate rather than filling in the details, which is cumbersome."*

Many participants needed assistance using this feature. Participant 12 said, *"I have used both Myntra and Nykaafashion. So, it was tough because the number of options they gave was like 1020 choices. While using a personal stylist, you need to be very specific; otherwise, it becomes confusing while chatting."*

It is mainly used for product discovery, but it sometimes becomes difficult to recall a brand's name; hence, giving commands to the stylist becomes irrelevant.

Participant 25 mentioned, *"The conversation needed to be more significant, responding very late with many breaks, leading to losing track of the talk and displaying unwanted options."*

Refer to [Table 2](#) to understand the themes and sub-themes of reasons for use and preference for virtual personal stylists.

Virtual personal stylists vs. physical in-person stylists

Chatbots and virtual personal stylists differ from conventional offline or online shopping assistants. Offline stores focus more on selling products than on understanding consumer expectations. Participant 2 said, *"They just want to sell the product. It may not suit you 100%, but they will make you feel like 100%,*

which has been suggested to others. But chatbots don't compel you to buy; you can take valuable inputs from them."

The transaction here is one-sided from the consumer to the brands and the suggestions and advice given to consumers. With such online shopping and the help of chatbots, you can buy a lot with one click. However, when we visit a store, one or two clothes are considered. Only that becomes the center, but when we are assisted during online purchases, *"so it becomes easy to buy two three products at that period,"* said Participant 7.

Participant 3 mentioned third opinion: *"shopping is mainly a friend or family experience. Social pressure is also not present at all when it comes to buying."*

Participant 9 discussed the freedom to purchase and leave the chatbot without pressure. *"It's different from somebody constantly standing on your head, entering the store without purchasing, and being awkward and embarrassed."*

The chatbots or these types of features don't have any emotional quotient.

"It's a software, It's a coding. So, they are giving you the standard option which you can find out while searching manually," said Participant 5.

Because artificial intelligence is involved and has a lot of memory, it can go through search and purchase history. It is like conversing with artificial intelligence, expect a better result.

Participant 10 said, *"What I have purchased lately could suggest better options, which I have been looking for. Maybe it should be well-informed about what kind of styles I like since the app is on Myntra."*

It is also meant to say about brand value and persona like Myntra, and suggestions from such brands are expected to be supreme. In addition, they must follow the price bracket judiciously. Participant 15 asked for saris in the range of 5k to 10k and found few were more than 10k and few in 1k and 3k. They work on decoding keywords and following their algorithm during interactions, which sometimes becomes confusing.

Participant 4 said, *"They will upgrade and update it to the level of consumer's thinking."*

According to Participant 4, at a store, it is possible to directly ask questions and easily make them understand your needs in a simple or local language, unlike just typing keywords. Humans touch matters because they have their perception and an emotional connection to understand the requirements. Thus, sales assistants have hands-on practical exposure, and on one look at personality, they recommend these new trends and fashion.

Participant 6 said that *"even if they give the vital stats to the chatbot, they are still determining exactly what sort of complexion/physical appearance they have. So, that detail or human touch needed to be improved in chatbots. Getting instant replies and affirmations from facial expressions gets things going well in a store. This is missing in this AI-style Chatbot; late replies mean a slow or uninterested flow of conversations."*

Participant 11 faced an issue each time they began the discussion. The Nykaafashion stylist AI wanted your number and email IDs, which was a problem. Responses also provided minimal responses to the questions.

Participant 11 said, *"Just because going back to tell them the phone number and email ID again, it's a waste of time and waste of energy, rather than thinking about design and the dress, gets concerned more about the numbers and email IDs."*

Chatbots show that, in addition to the mentioned category of clothes, they smartly and conveniently introduce party wear; they combine it so thoughtfully that consumers will not understand, but ultimately, they could have given some disclaimers.

According to Participant 25, *"in-store experience can't be matched to buying clothes and trying them there, which is a great physical experience."*

Reservations or obstacles in usage-Influencing factors

Any reservations or obstacles could prevent from using a chatbot or virtual personal stylist. The keyword search in the Myntra chat option shows that they have algorithmic issues in decoding consumer responses.

Participant 7 reflected *"with Google that a search where comparison with other apps will also be readily available. It's possible to compare the prices of the same piece of cloth on various shopping apps. Even the response must be on time, degrading the conversation flow rate on Nykaafashion."*

Table 3. Themes and sub-themes on Reservations or Obstacles in Usage-Influencing Factors.

Theme	Sub-themes
User Experience Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of human touch • Confusion due to keyword search • Ineffective Communication • Technical limitations and lag • Limited Personalization
Privacy and Security Concerns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Privacy concerns • Robotic Interaction • Unwanted Product Promotions
Decision-Making Difficulties	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pushy product recommendation • Overwhelming options • Difficulty in Specificity • Reduced research efforts but limits choices
Preference and Familiarity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preference for traditional shopping • Limited use for special occasions • Clear-cut shopping preferences
Emotional Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of emotional sensitivity • Need for brand specificity
Efficiency and Performance Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time-consuming and frustrating lag

Participant 11 said, *"The conversation became disengaging and uninterested. It was also observed that they were pushing certain products while chatting. After they have shown a list of options and want to add something else to our information, they again start from the beginning, only like the first query, which is repeated sometimes. That becomes a tiresome job."*

According to Participant 4, *"They are recommending related products which are of no interest. They are just advertising the new things, but the consumer will currently look for priority stuff."*

Participant 24 mentions, *"There's no representative, so it's just robotic dialogue, and it is only on a command base." The most common concern was missing human touch.*

Participant 21 said, *"This feature has recently started, so it never felt like they were pushing any products to buy. This has lessened research efforts but limited broad vision, as it shapes the mind to look for specific designs as it is trendy. Even the information quality provided during the conversation was very generic/vague."*

Participant 22 said, *"Don't remember the names of many brands where filters help. But here, we have to be specific about brands." The conversation style should be more personalised rather than following the same pattern for everyone.*

Refer to Table 3 to understand the different obstacles in the usage influencing factors. A few people did not find any negatives, but only minor transformations or additions. Participant 2 said, *"The only thing is that it's their policy or something, and they cannot dedicate plenty of time to one consumer."*

Additionally, Participant 7 *"mentioned that the options displayed were higher than required; otherwise, there would have been no issue. In Nykaafashion, on the other side of the chatbot are the actual stylists; they don't give time to see the options or explore it and leave the chat, ask to again get in touch and take the stylist's name, then they can join in again, as it is WhatsApp integrated."*

Hence, Participant 2 said, *"they will have access to the consumer's profile photo and mobile number, which can be a privacy breach. Instead, they believed they won't misuse data because they already have a huge customer base."*

Research and decision-making influence

Using chatbots or virtual personal stylists has changed how research is conducted before purchasing apparel.

According to Participant 2, *"The hectic research time has been reduced by the help of Nykaafashion stylists. That means, after this feature, it's like relying more on personal stylists than your research."*

According to Participant 4, *"The description needs to be read to understand the quality and design of the apparel. But the thing is, the AI chatbots, with the help of it, don't have to scroll to the bottom of the product page and click through the details. It is a valuable thing that we don't have to scroll the whole page; it will just show the product details as we asked for."*

For Participant 9, *“window shopping with friends will be converted to chatbots for a second opinion.”*

Participant 16 adopted a strategy in place. *“Now that there is a chatbot, first open the Myntra chatbot. Secondly, open the virtual personal stylist of Nykaafashion and ask them the same questions. If the options provided 50% match, go with Myntra; otherwise, go with Nykaafashion and compare. So, this is how the pattern has changed.”*

Participant 25 also shared the same views; ratings and reviews were of prime concern, and the price was lower in some apps than in others. Therefore, it is preferable to check for available discounts.

Influence of virtual personal stylists on purchase choices

The help of chatbots or virtual personal stylists affects your decisions and influences your purchase choice. Participant 2 generated trust because he received what he required or was looking for.

Participant 14 said, *“They might be influenced to buy when the product is in their mind.”*

Participant 15 agreed that Nykaafashion’s stylist influenced them to buy. Participant 24 is fascinated by receiving advice from such stylists, just like big celebrities; it is like they are helping to form an opinion.

A few participants, like 3, prefer it sometimes because these platforms have too many collections and tend to get confused; when suggestions are limited, such as five or six, it is easier to decide likes and dislikes, and you can also try to see different collections with similar types of designs. They cannot have such an influence, but Participant 13 said, *“It might lead them to think because of just one thing that the chatbot has all the past conversations that can be referred to.”*

Participant 17 also felt that *“it has to be constant with its good performance to build trust; otherwise, it might fall back to search and filters because of habits.”*

According to Participant 19, *“I’ll say the success rate for it is three and two times. So, it’s not always a hit every time. Sometimes it is they give you what you want. Sometimes it doesn’t work out.”*

Participant 25 was doubtful about a final purchase based on their recommendations, at maximum, putting that on favourites or wishlists so that I could buy it in the future. This influence can be on the mind, but not on direct conversion or purchase.

Participant 4 negated the chatbot’s influence on making purchases. According to a few, Myntra Chatbot is terrible, while Nykaafashion is much more personalized. Now, I have sufficient experience in shopping or surfing apps. It is habitual, and I have multiple filters in mind under this budget. One believes only in themselves unless they are satisfied with their own eyes and does not believe so. These chatbot features recently feed on preferences and stuff. However, they must show the expected options. Participant 16 disagreed that, as its functionality depends upon the user’s input, it extracts some text and analyses from the database regarding that text. They display the output, but they do not find the context or meaning of the sentence. What disappointed Participant 21 was the limited content for plus size; the personal assistant denied giving any suggestions based on size. Participant 20 thought that this was an irrelevant feature.

Buying patterns

There were changes in the shopping habits of participants since they started using chatbots or virtual personal stylists. For Participant 2, *“a lot has changed, like spending less time on the app but meaningful time for shopping. The search was for pre-decided apparel, as scrolling takes a lot of time, but now, much time has been saved for looking at more things.”*

Participant 3 became a shopaholic and bought more clothes with a personal assistant than they did by themselves because research used to take a lot of time, like digging the app and needing more clarification about the information provided, unlike now it’s all clear. Table 4 lists the factors influencing the decision-making process.

According to Participant 17, *“the frequency of using chatbots has increased compared to using a website.”* Participant 23 agreed to have been influenced. Participant 19 has a different take; *“as a fashionista given a chance to navigate and experiment with various outfits, it was never in mind that it works best as an advisor.”*

Table 4. Themes and sub-themes on research and decision-making influence.

Theme	Sub-themes
Influence of Personal Stylists	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trust Building • Conversion influence
User Preferences and Habits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategy development • Platform trust and preferences • Habitual shopping behavior • Doubtful conversion
Functionality and Performance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Functionality Limitations • Context Understanding • Content Relevance
User Skepticism and Doubt	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Skepticism about recommendations • Limited confidence in chatbot suggestions • Irrelevance and disappointment

Table 5. Themes and sub-themes on buying patterns.

Theme	Sub-themes
Increased Efficiency and Confidence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time-saving Shopping • Enhanced confidence in purchases • Frequency of usage
Influence and Satisfactions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Influence on purchasing behavior • Satisfaction with recommendations • Faith in AI system
Inconsistencies and Doubts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Situational effectiveness • Inconsistency in recommendations • Validation and satisfaction
User Interface and Functionality Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User interface concerns • Lack of understanding of human inputs • Disappointment with options provided • Delays and frustrations in conversation

Participant 5 discusses the Nykaafashion WhatsApp integration as a milestone: *“it’s like always chatting”*, whereas for Participant 7, *“everything has stayed the same.”*

Participant 11 hesitated to use it because they could have been more accurate and fluent in conversations with many breaks and limited responses. Participant 20 said, *“They provided 70% of recommendations with the required apparel or something that needed to be asked for and needed clarification.”*

Participant 24 said, *“I will buy it in advance, even if it is required post two months, and do extra shopping for months. Even if there is no need for clothing, I will end up buying so much.”*

For Participant 22, other than the budget, everything else has little influence. Refer to [Table 5](#) for themes and subthemes of Buying Patterns.

Effect on user confidence

Chatbots or virtual personal stylists make you feel more confident or satisfied with their purchases. Participant 2 has agreed that *“it makes them feel more confident or satisfied. It feels like an introduction of assurance; previously, unless the product was delivered, we were doubtful about the product, so we wore it and got reviews from everybody else. But with the help of a personal stylist, they suggest an excellent product that they’ll assure you will look good and that is the best possible product available for that particular consumer. The experience has improved and has become more customer-centric.”*

A better word for this would be individual-centric. Participant 9 said, *“Yes, of course, because they know the new trend, what’s new in fashion.”*

Participant 3 still had confidence but faith in the AI system. Participant 17 agreed with the reference. According to Participant 12, *“it is very situational; sometimes, they suggest extraordinary dresses, and sometimes, there are no matches. Hence, this inconsistency leads to a lot of doubts.”*

Participant 14 talked about the ultimate validation from the husband. According to Participant 19, *“It’s just satisfactory, not too good, not too bad, but acceptable in the sense that they cut down the number of options, but not exactly what’s required, but around the range, the type of dress or the brand according to body anatomically.”*

According to Participant 4, *"the user interface could have been more user-friendly; hence, it was supposed to ask too many questions, specify too many details, and not get satisfactory answers."*

Participant 5 added, *"I still feel it's too primitive to understand humans."* Participant 7 also seemed disappointed as the options provided were of different types and from other collections with various budgets. Participant 11 agreed with them, as a few options were outside the budget. They were two to three times the budget. Participant 20 seemed upset because going through with this conversation delays, spending five minutes waiting for the guy to join, and then another five minutes discussing and sharing the media snapshot of the all-brand product in Nykaafashion.

Engagement and personalisation

Virtual personal stylists and chatbots improve the customization of your buying experience, and their suggestions match your interests and unique styles. Participant 2 said, *"Out of 6 or 7 options, 2-3 options matched the interest by making them particular brands, colour, fashion wear, budget, etc. They understood the requirements in a better fashion."*

Participant 14 also found at least one item relevant to imagined style. Participant 6 also agreed that this matched her interests.

Participant 16 said, *"There is a high chance that you will like some of the options."* Participant 7 was happy, that they were doing half the job. Otherwise, I must look over the entire set of collections. Participant 19 validated this: *"Personal assistant chatbot shows five outfits for five different occasions; the success rate for it is at least two or three."* Participant 13 said, *"It's 50-50."* Participant 8 disagreed that the notching matches. According to Participant 11, *"the options provided were outside the budget and could have been more satisfactory."* Participant 15 said, *"was not in the range. The second thing is the irrelevant option. The third thing was the response time."* Refer to [Table 6](#) to check the customization and personalisation of the buying experience.

Virtual personal stylists and chatbots eventually take on the role of personalized services provided by high-end brick-and-mortar stores. Participant 2 agreed that *"it can be implemented, that people can get valuable inputs like a good recommendation, and that people will be happy to take it if it comes from a professional."*

Participant 3 said, *"It would be helpful as in-store sales assistants are present, not stylists. There is no sales assistant in the Mumbai Ajo store; this personalised service was incorporated as it is entirely automatic."*

Participant 5 said, *"We will be just looking at the screen, and we will be dressed and be shown two to three outfits and by clicking the option, costume changes automatically to that one; our generation is more fashion conscious than ever, like previous generations or the coming generations."*

Participant 5 mentions *"a movie with a scene for time travel to 2050 and shops from a virtual stylist, and there is a screen, like a mirror or something."*

Participant 9 talks about the value addition in big franchise stores such as Zara and Mango, but it will make little sense to small stores. Participant 19 felt that it would be a well-designated job.

According to Participant 11, *"It should have a good response speed in real-time, which is the future, but currently, it's difficult."*

Table 6. Themes and sub-themes on engagement and personalisation.

Theme	Sub-themes
Enhanced Personalisation:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efficient Recommendations: Saves time • Reflects unique style: Matches Interests • Customization Need: Specific requirements
Current Role of AI Stylists	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seamless Integration: Offline Stores • Human Replacement: Cost Effective • AR/VR Integration: Enhanced Experience
Customer Satisfaction and Confidence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfactory Suggestions: Boosts confidence • Future Improvement: Expectations met • Trust in AI: Reliable Assistance
Efficiency and Convenience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time-saving: Streamlined Process • Effort Reduction: Simplifies Decision making • Convenience: Easy access, Quick responses

Participant 23 said, *"It will be labour who does the task; this is more in terms of business because this technology is going to be so cheaper in future it is it will be more cost-effective for any company to have than human to assist as a lot have to be hired."*

According to 24, screens of chatbots or virtual personal stylists could not be a permanent solution in stores, as many customers need many screens, which makes no sense. Additionally, Participant 25 said, *"Chatbot should not only be in the text mode, it should be in audio or video mode as well."*

Future use and recommendations

Chatbots and virtual personal stylists are evolving in the shopping world and will be used in the future, based on your experience. Participant 2 discussed the most critical component, saving time and providing valuable suggestions.

Participant 3 feels *"it's a reasonable assistance in advice for a consumer and a professional human stylist."*

Participant 7 said, *"Yes, of course, aspiration. It's like experiencing something new; Gen Z is there for everything new. It's going to grow."*

Participant 12 did not want to visit the store and remained indoors. Participant 16 expected this feature to be fun in the future. Participant 5 thinks there's a 50-50% chance that many influencers promote their styles and that people like to wear them. Even Myntra has an influencer-style feature where consumers buy clothes from influencers, such as how they wear them; this is more situational. Participant 17 found it difficult to change the search and filtering habits; otherwise, it was good to go. Participant 19 was critical when he talked about the older generation being non-tech savvy; the divide between the younger generations makes all the differences.

Participant 13 said, *"No, don't think so."* Participant 20 needed to be sure of its use.

Participant 1 recommended the option of specific filtering and personalization of information quality in conversation and adding filters from the app to the chatbots in different forms. Participant 2 wanted to have a picture shared instead of the link and integrate AI and VR/AR (pictures, audio, and video). Participant 3 knew the regional language and felt more comfortable; hence, the chatbot had to converse in the local language.

Participant 4 wants *"ease of navigation, unlike WhatsApp integration in Nykaafashion or searching for this option in Myntra."*

Participant 5 thought that it had to be more than a keyword search. Participant 5 discussed the following: *"Don't show sponsored products at the start and irrelevant categories like complete outfit suggestion."*

Participant 5 wanted a notification if they had similar products available in their inventory and added a memory to the Chatbot feature. Participants 8 and 9 recommended being more humanistic; hence, filtering should be more precise and personalized. Participant 6 was concerned about integrating other support tools, data privacy, and security, which would help enhance the chatbot. Therefore, additional customization is required. Participant 10 emphasized the importance of understanding a consumer's personality type and style and called it a consumer chatbot, a consumer-oriented chatbot. According to Participant 14, Myntra should come up with different personality types; basically, for personality analysis also, they do have data for not only the person who shops but if the person is shopping for three other people who have data for those three particular people. They used it for size recommendations. Thus, it can do the same for personal stylists and style recommendations. Refer to [Table 7](#) to check for future upgrades to make it more robust.

Participant 12 recommends *"using digital data, tracking the journey through their consumer profile, and then discussing the purchase."*

Participant 15 was frustrated about their slow speed and late responses and tended to miss many thoughts going through their minds. Participant 16 said that they were slightly changing the options with different commands. They shuffled the options and displayed the results; this needs to be more personalized. It also adds that they are ignorant about consumer identities, and, while conversing, they should go from generic to specific questions. According to Participant 17, AI should be combined at least one human presence, primarily mainly an AI human-assisted system.

Table 7. Themes and sub-themes on Future Use and Recommendations.

Theme	Sub-themes
Integration and Compatibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cross-platform Functionality • Seamless API integration • Compatibility with existing systems
Personalisation and Customisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multi-channel accessibility • User Profile tailoring • Adaptive recommendations • Customise responses • Dynamic content delivery
Advancements in AI and Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Natural Language Processing enhancement • Machine learning algorithms • Sentiment analysis integration • Contextual understanding
User Experience Enhancement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved Interface design • Interactive features • Real-time feedback Incorporation • Enhanced support and assistant
Enhancing User-Friendliness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visual Integration • Multilingual support • Precise filtering • Real-time notification • Humanised interaction

In addition, it discusses the seamless placement of this feature in an application. Participant 18 *“discourages customer typing, introduces multimodal concepts, and endorses voice-to-text, speech-to-text, etc.”*

Participant 19 needed help to come to that particular feature while navigating through the entire app; hence, finding that specific features become a task. Participant 20 feels *“it’s suitable for the Discovery Process but still needs to decide on the assistant level. Therefore, the interface can be interactive, and people like to use it often.”*

Participant 21 recommended adding specific filtering while conversing, personalizing information quality, and adding filters in the form of text from the app to the chatbots. Participant 22 gave an example of incorporating real-time weather forecasts into trips, saying that they should include such features and add pictures to chatbots. This gives them an extra edge, where the consumer is updated with critical information. Participant 23 mentioned that the chatbot with augmented reality in the future could be the next big thing. Participant 25 discussed the importance of history, past purchases, and decision-making. Participant 24 argued that it should show more options rather than forcing a particular kind of brand or pattern; it should follow all the cultures and be more towards the users with whom they use this feature.

According to Participant 11, *“The most impacting reason is the budget, which can be increased to certain limits but cannot be twice or thrice a particular amount because that will be a debt. Hence, it can display products slightly above but not more than that.”*

Table 7 outlines the themes and sub-themes of future use and recommendations for virtual styling chatbots or agents.

Conclusion

Customers will eventually outsource their decision-making to computers that mimic humans. According to Sidlauskienė et al. (2023), consumers can evaluate products better because AI-powered chatbots use anthropomorphic speech cues to simulate human-like interactions. The findings of this research resonate with the importance of the linguistic style used during conversation to execute the purchase; it either helps to build faith or loses interest. Epley et al. (2008) suggested that people attempt to compensate for their loneliness by connecting with non-human materials resembling humans. Further, Sidlauskienė et al. (2023) indicated that when participants engaged with an anthropomorphic chatbot and felt more situationally lonely, they were willing to spend an excellent price on goods.

This study suggests that even during loneliness, consumers see chatbot suggestions as an option rather than a decision-making factor. Hence, payment comes much later; they can wishlist it, but not pay for it. According to Hoo et al. (2023), ease of use and usefulness had a favourable and significant impact on chatbot adoption. Even if ease and usefulness exist, there is no privacy and security system, and consistency in good options is absent throughout the commerce journey; social impact also plays a

critical role. Otherwise, experience becomes irrelevant. In addition, Nichifor et al. (2021), chatbots' main issues are their inability to be personalized, the timing of their responses, and texts that could be more relevant to the customers' questions. To increase user engagement and commitment, stress the significance of chatbots exhibiting technical proficiency in conducting conversations and providing observable response times. This study supports the above author, as it emphasizes the need for personalization, downplays response lag, and the need for more than just textual understanding between the consumer and chatbot. Araújo et al. (2022) state that, although many brands, particularly those in the fast fashion industry, offer chatbots, they do not engage customers as much as recommendation systems.

Nevertheless, many customers find it helpful, particularly before purchasing. This is because they provide highly customized customer support, which reduces the obstacle to finding the right product. In addition, the findings show that product discovery is why consumers use chatbots. It is usually due to less time taken and might leave few from numerous available options, but chatbots skim and provide the best of it.

Consumers have used chatbots or virtual personal stylists mainly for recommendations from friends or accidentally while scrolling they saw this new feature. It can be observed from two different giants, Myntra and Nykaafashion, that the two propound the use of chatbots. It provides good insight into the two chatbots; one is integrated into the app, and the latter is WhatsApp integration. Hence, consumers prefer the in-app integration of Myntra because Nykaafashion might face privacy concerns. Nykaafashion, the options provided, were liked by many as the stylist on the other side was human, but Myntra had fully automated conversations. Participant 2 said, "I used the Nykafashion platform. The experience has been excellent because personalized options have been suggested." The options provided by human stylists are few and considerable. Still, Myntra gave 1000 options, which became a burden and irrelevant to the budget mentioned. It appeared more like a command-based conversation, which was time-consuming. The humanized AI of NykaaFashion seems to be more engaging and culturally inclusive, and the issues have been proactively resolved. The earlier conversation with the chatbot was lost, but Nykaafashion retained it; hence, returning to it became easier. Thus, consumers using Nykaafashion virtual stylists were more satisfied than those using Myntra chatbots, but many upgrades were still required.

During the interview, it was observed that consumers can see problems from the industry they belong to, but not solely as consumers. The fashion and marketing professional stated AI chatbots and virtual stylists can be trained to make sustainable fashion recommendations. These tools can, for instance, recommend apparel made of organic materials, goods from companies with a solid reputation for environmental responsibility, or goods with a lower carbon footprint. Experts in the visual design and IT sectors characterized it as a prompt-driven search, a problem in exploration is the incorporation of emotional intelligence (EI) into AI chatbots. Others thought of it as a resource for insightful advice and as a means of getting expert assistance when shopping for clothes. One may argue that when customer segmentation improved chatbot functionality—such as behavioural aspects, apparel recommendations, fashion consultations, etc.—the goal of the technology shifted. While information gatherers rely on chatbots for in-depth product insights and comparisons, convenience seekers use them for rapid navigation and frictionless transactions. Chatbots are used by bargain hunters to locate sales and promotions, and by help seekers to track orders and resolve problems. Chatbots are useful for explorers to find ideas and products, and personalized shoppers value them for their customized recommendations. Comprehending these diverse interactions can aid in enhancing chatbot performance to more effectively satisfy the varying needs of e-commerce customers. It was also observed that Men and women differ in their choices for communication styles, recommendations trends etc. Female participants had more privacy concerns, data breaches, and the accuracy of recommendations than men.

This study discusses the usefulness of chatbots to the consumer side and uses the co-creation theory to understand the association of Chatbots/Virtual Personal Stylists as brand side and its impact. Chatbots use machine learning to identify trends and repeat actions, but they represent the brand image. Based on individual preferences, tailoring recommendations and interactions aligns with the above theory, where customers actively participate rather than being passive recipients. Although AI-driven technologies are highly efficient, the depth of co-creation can be limited by their inability to reproduce human empathy. This highlights the need for better emotional intelligence to involve users fully in the process. The quality of co-creation is directly impacted by the urgency around chatbot design features. The

co-creation process runs more smoothly and productively thanks to these above features, which facilitate more rewarding and natural interactions.

According to Hoo et al. (2023), companies strive to provide customers with the best possible online experience, which includes offering virtual assistants, seamless online interactions, and personalized recommendation systems as customers surf the Internet regularly. This can be more effectively used to support business marketing plans. In e-commerce, AI-powered chatbots can better understand consumer preferences, create predictive models of personalities, and present them with tailored offers. Chatbots can be used in e-commerce to sell customized products and attract prospective customers (Sidlauskiene et al., 2023). Organizations can implement several strategies to remove obstacles, offer tailored assistance, and provide trendy products. However, to strengthen their bonds with customers, businesses must be transparent about how they respond. With a quick response time, people are encouraged to contact the provider because they know that they will hear back immediately (Nichifor et al., 2021). The effectiveness of conversational commerce can also be noted after virtual stylist and chatbot interaction, such as conversion rates, sales impact, customer retention, customer engagement, data insights, and brand perception.

Consumers mainly use chatbots to gain insights into specific fashions and take advice about trends in product discovery and recommendations. They have hands-on experience with services available to celebrities, as they consider chatbots their budding stage. Even if a few consumers are still dissatisfied with the conversation style, response times, navigation through the app, etc., they would still like to use it, as this will be part of their pre-purchase decision. Consumers did not complain about any product interface design, cross-selling, or upselling. Instead, they talked about conversational flow, such as difficulty in intent recognition, entity recognition, and contextual understanding, but they could decode the text and comprehend the language.

Consumers wanted to have a multimodal interface, such as voice-to-text, image-based, etc., with cultural sensitivity and emotional AI incorporated; the approach has to be more regional than global. The study includes every aspect of chatting options about fashion and its trends, consumers' mindset while using this feature, and brands' takeaways. As apps have recently been introduced, it has become essential to understand the awareness about the perceived value propagation to consumers, which shapes brand perception further, such as Myntra, Nyaafashion, etc.

Contribution to theory and practice

The concept of a virtual personal stylist and chatbot is a recent phenomenon of great importance because it affects budget, lifestyle, and social identity to a great extent. This study opens up new research and theory development directions related to styling, advising, and recommending in digital e-commerce. This study looks at the motivational factors associated with the discovery of the features' likes or dislikes by understanding the usage pattern of the feature and purchasing apparel by using theoretical lenses of co-creation theory between the consume and brand sides in the digital e-commerce app, mainly Nykaafashiona and Myntra.

They add to prior research that has been done in the field of chatting and the evolution of chatbots as stylists in the fashion industry. This study raises new questions, such as how virtual personal stylists have changed how consumers conduct research before buying apparel. As applicable, theoretical and conceptual model development and testing using quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods are based on inductive or deductive reasoning. Based on these findings, practitioners in the fast-fashion industry and online businesses such as SMEs can develop strategies by gathering insights for further campaigns or upgrades.

For practitioners, this study sensitizes and argues for the need to develop AI-human-assisted chatbots for consumers in the digital public sphere. The study neither supports nor critiques the role of new technologies, as this feature has scope for improvement.

Future scope

- Future research should refine these results by evaluating how chatbots impact the willingness to pay a higher product price by creating the perception of product personalization and generating trust

by understanding consumer intentions. Consumer intentions can be studied if chatbots are a strategic way of advertising or seamlessly pushing a product.

- Future studies can be conducted on the effect of AI-humanized stylists introduced by employing chatbots to sell personalized sustainable products and update users with upcoming discounts.
- Future research could investigate how cultural orientation and language in chatbot characteristics can impact consumer purchasing decisions during interactions. Another intriguing area of inquiry may be the growth of algorithmic consumers and society delegating decision-making to bots and personal information disclosure concerns.

Limitation

- The study ignored possible interactions with visual or auditory signals, which can have different effects on consumers' views, and instead focused exclusively on verbal anthropomorphic cues.
- The study did not investigate the privacy risks of AI-powered chatbots gathering personal information that could affect customer confidence and behavior.
- This study's emphasis on Indian respondents may have limited the generalizability of its findings by failing to consider cultural differences in how people react to anthropomorphic chatbots.
- The lack of wholesome use due to its recent introduction could have given more focus to a single or few topics such as personalization and improper timing of responses in chatbots, which may have restricted their efficacy at this budding point of development and did not explore the brand side much.

Author contributions

Ashwini Ranjan: Conceptualization, Formal Analysis, Methodology, Data Collection and Analysis, Writing – Original draft, Writing – Review and Editing. Ashwani Kumar Upadhyay: Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – Original draft, Writing – Review and Editing.

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Discussion guide

1. Please introduce yourself and provide some background on your knowledge and physical or online purchasing experience of fashion apparel.
2. Have you ever used a chatbot-based or virtual personal stylist when contemplating or purchasing apparel? If so, kindly share your experience(s) with us.
3. What encouraged you to purchase based on suggestions or the help of a chatbot or a virtual personal stylist? Was it for real-time efficiency, an update on trends, new collections, fashion advice, suggestions based on past purchases, offers personalized loyalty programs, post-buying advice, or providing real-time, data-driven recommendations, or any opportunities for co-creation?
4. How do chatbots and virtual personal stylists differ from conventional in-store or online shopping assistants?
5. What motivates you to consult a chatbot or virtual personal stylist while purchasing fashion apparel?
6. Are there any reservations or obstacles that could keep you from using a chatbot or virtual personal stylist?
7. How has using chatbots or virtual personal stylists changed the way you conduct research before making an apparel purchase? Did it help you obtain information or hinder you?
8. Did the help of chatbots or virtual personal stylists affect your decisions? If so, how did they influence your choice to make the purchase?
9. Since you started using chatbots or virtual personal stylists for shopping, have you seen any changes in your shopping habits?

10. Do chatbots or virtual personal stylists make you feel more confident or satisfied about your purchases? How has this changed your purchasing experience as a whole?
11. How do virtual personal stylists and chatbots improve the customization of your buying experience? Do their suggestions match your interests and unique style?
12. Would virtual personal stylists and chatbots eventually take the role of personalized service provided by high-end brick-and-mortar stores?
13. How do you see chatbots and virtual personal stylists evolving in shopping? Will it be used in the future?
14. How may chatbots and virtual personal stylists be made more successful and user-friendly? What features might they add? (Recommendations)?

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About the authors

Ashwini Ranjan, Ph.D. Scholar, Symbiosis Institute of Media and Communication, Symbiosis International (Deemed University), Pune, Maharashtra, India. Ms. Ranjan is currently enrolled in the Ph.D. program of Symbiosis International (Deemed University), Pune as a full-time Junior Research Fellow. She completed her MBA in the Media and Communication field in 2022. She has a keen interest in technology-enabled new ways of communication in the political sphere, and mixed research.

Ashwani Kumar Upadhyay, Ph.D., Professor, Symbiosis Institute of Media and Communication, Symbiosis International (Deemed University), Pune, Maharashtra, India. Dr. Upadhyay is Professor and the author of book “AI revolution in HRM: The New Scorecard.” He has more than 23 years of experience. He earned first position in the AIMS-GHSIMR Doctoral Student Paper Competition at IIM, Ahmedabad. His research interests span artificial intelligence, virtual reality, augmented reality, technology adoption, and branding.

Data availability statement

The corresponding author can provide data upon reasonable request.

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